

Synthesis and physicochemical studies of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes with various Schiff bases containing oxygen and nitrogen donor atoms

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The complexes of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) of the types $[(sb)_2M.2H_2O]$ [where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}], [sbH = sapH, napH], [(Cl)Cu(sb)] and [Cu(sb)₂] [sb = sapH, smabH] have been prepared by using simple metathetic reactions. The structural characterization of the complexes, synthesized during the present course of investigations have been elucidated by elemental analysis (C, H, N, Cl and Cu), IR, electronic spectral data, ESR, FAB-MS and magnetic studies. Thermogravimetric studies have also been carried out for some of the hydrated metal complexes.

Keywords: Schiff base, IR, ESR, thermogravimetric analysis.

Introduction

The chemistry of Schiff bases has developed because of their ease of synthesis and fair solubility in common organic solvents¹. It is one of the most widely used ligands due to their various applications in the analytical chemistry, dye industry², food industry³, agrochemical⁴, fungicidal⁴, catalysis⁵ and biological activities⁵ and therefore it played a significant role in the coordination chemistry. Schiff base metal complexes are of great interest in chelation therapy for the treatment of heavy-metal poisoning and biomedical research^{6,7}. As copper is a trace element in the human body and works as cofactor in enzymes and other structures⁸. Schiff bases containing nitrogen and oxygen donors have a variety of ways in which they are coordinated to the metal ions⁹.

Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde/naphthaldehyde were involved in O-H...N or O...H-N type intramolecular hydrogen bond¹⁰. It also shows keto-amine and enol-imine tautomerism. A higher value of the activation energy of salicylaldehyde de-

rived metal complexes makes it highly thermal stable¹¹. Schiff bases derived from heterocyclic amines containing -N=CH- (imines) group was significant in illuminating the mechanism of racemisation and transamination reactions in living organisms¹¹. The metal complexes were found to be in different geometrical form such as copper(II) complexes are square planar, cobalt(II) is tetrahedral while nickel(II) is octahedral.

In present course of investigation, we report herein synthesis and spectroscopic studies of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) Schiff base complexes. An octahedral geometry around cobalt(II) is also reported¹² only on the basis of coordination with two H₂O molecules.

Results and discussion

Cobalt(II) and copper(II) complexes with sapH (salicylidene-2-aminopyridene) and cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes with napH (naphthalene-2-aminopyridene) were found to be soluble in hot DMF, DMSO and 1,4-dioxane, whereas

insoluble in alcohol, acetone and chloroform, except for copper(II) napH complexes which is soluble in hot chloroform. The proposed structure of Schiff bases and their complexes are given below:

where M = Co, Cu, Ni and "O/N" – sapH (1, 2, 6 and 7), napH (3-5) and smabH (8-9)

Whereas Schiff base complexes of copper(II) of the types, [(Cl)Cu(sap)] and [(Cl)Cu(smab)], as well as [Cu(smab)₂] and [Cu(sap)₂] have been prepared by the reaction of copper(II)chloride (anhydrous) with sodium salt of Schiff bases [sapH and smabH (salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene)] in 1:1 and 1:2 molar ratio(s), in the presence of THF-C₆H₆ mixture, which can be illustrated by the following chemical equations:

[where; sbH = smabH and sapH]

Infrared spectral studies:

The infrared spectra of the Schiff base exhibited characteristic stretching frequency¹³ in the region 3420–3280 cm⁻¹ due to presence of (phenolic) -OH group. These bands have been disappeared¹⁴ in the spectra of the complexes suggesting the involvement of 'O' atom in the bonding after deprotonation of phenolic group. Bands appeared in the range 1270–

1269 cm⁻¹ may ascribe to ν_{C=O} stretching frequency in the Schiff bases, which was shifted to higher frequency¹⁴ region suggesting the coordination through 'O' atom to the metal ion, which was further supported by the appearance of new bands^{15–17} in the region 540–320 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{M–O}. The ligands also showed a strong bands in the region 1647–1590 cm⁻¹, assigned to ν_{C=N} vibration¹³ after coordination is shifted to lower frequency¹⁴ region 1619–1580 cm⁻¹. In metal complexes this negative shift and appearance of new bands^{15–17} in the region 525–352 cm⁻¹ shows the participation of the azomethine nitrogen in the coordination of metal. A broad band is observed in the complexes 1–5 in the range 3379–3428 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{OH} of coordinated water. This is supported by appearance of an additional band in the range 840–800 cm⁻¹ for (O-H) rocking deformation. The new bands also appear in the range 750–710 cm⁻¹ which is not observed in the ligand spectrum.

Electronic spectral studies:

The electronic spectral data of metal complexes are consistent with the octahedral geometry around cobalt(II) and nickel(II) atom whereas copper(II) complexes are distorted due to Jahn-Teller effect. These values are consistent with the literature^{18,19}.

All these ligands exhibit characteristic bands at 28145 ± 18, 32000 ± 150 and 36000 ± 400 cm⁻¹ which may be due to n-π*, π-π* and n-σ* transition. These bands slightly red shifted in complexes. Besides these bands two more band were observed in the metal complexes at around 21008 and 23201 cm⁻¹ which may be attributed to charge transfer bands from ligand to metal.

Magnetic studies:

The copper(II) complexes of 3d⁹ configuration exhibits paramagnetism corresponding to one unpaired spin (S = 1/2 μ_{spin only} = 1.73 B.M.). However, magnetic moment is usually observed to be slightly higher ~ 2.0 B.M. Stereochemistry of copper(II) complexes are expected to have little effect on magnetic moment of cupric ion, which should be with a spin-orbit coupling constant of λ = -850 cm⁻¹, about 1.9 B.M. at room temperature.

The magnetic moment values²⁰ observed for chloro-bridged complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Cu}_2(\text{smab})_2]$ exhibited slightly lower value (1.60–1.53 B.M.) than spin only value (1.73 B.M.); indicated antiferromagnetic super exchange phenomenon between two copper(II) centres through, chlorine form dimeric structure.

Thermogravimetric studies:

The thermogravimetric data^{21–23} (Fig. 1, Supplementary Figs. S1 and S2) shows the presence of two molecules of water in the complexes. $[\text{Co}(\text{sap})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{nap})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ complex loose water molecules in the temperature range of 80°C and 160°C, respectively. The percentage water loss is also equivalent to two moles in each compound. It is indicated by the observed values of 7.67 and 6.08 which are approximately equal to the calculated values of 7.39 and 6.13 for **sapH** and **napH** complexes, respectively. The complexes decomposes at temperature range of 200–720°C and 160–760°C for **sapH** and **napH**, respectively. The final residue in both the cases is consistent with the weight of CoO.

Fig. 1. TG curve of complexes $[\text{Co}(\text{nap})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{nap})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{nap})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$.

Nickel(II) complexes of **napH** also show the presence of two mole of water. The value of 6.27 found, is quite close to the calculated value of 6.13 for two water molecules. The complexes loose water slowly up to 200°C and then undergoes abrupt decomposition and continues up to 720°C and showing sharp fall again at this temperature and then becomes con-

stant and corresponds to NiO.

Copper(II) complexes start decomposing at 80°C in both the cases. The loss of water molecules continues up to 160°C and 200°C in **sapH** and **napH** complexes, respectively. The values of percentage water loss are 7.46 and 5.82 for **sapH** and **napH** complexes respectively. These values are quite close to the calculated values of 7.32 for **sapH** and 6.08 for **napH** complexes of copper. The copper(II)-**sapH** complex decomposes at temperature 200°C and the decomposition continues up to 760°C and there after it attains a constant composition corresponding to CuO. The **napH** complex of copper on the other hand decomposes temperature range of 200–680°C and the residue does not correspond to simple mono oxide and is believed to be a mixture of oxides CuO and Cu_2O ²³.

ESR spectral studies:

ESR spectra of copper(II) complexes (Fig. 2), such as $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Cu}_2(\text{smab})_2]$, $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Cu}_2(\text{sap})_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{smab})_2]$ have been measured in polycrystalline solid state at room temperature. Copper(II) system studies herein, showed a pronounced peak for which $g_{\perp} \cong 1.99$, and a broad shallow quadruplet peak, for which $g_{\parallel} \cong 2.29$. The higher value of g_{\parallel} in compare to g_{\perp} suggests the presence of unpaired electron in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital.

Fig. 2. ESR spectra of $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Cu}_2(\text{smab})_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{smab})_2]$.

Table 1. ESR spectral data of some copper(II) complexes containing various Schiff bases

Sl. No.	Complex	Field (Gauss)		g_{\perp}	g_{\parallel}	g_{av}
		H_{\parallel}	H_{\perp}			
1	$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Cu}_2(\text{sap})_2]$ 6	3080	3420	1.98	2.20	2.05
2	$[\text{Cu}(\text{sap})_2]$ 7	2820	3320	2.07	2.40	2.18
3	$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Cu}_2(\text{smab})_2]$ 8	3060	3400	1.99	2.21	2.06
4	$[\text{Cu}(\text{smab})_2]$ 9	2800	3440	1.97	2.42	2.12

The g_{av} values were calculated according to the relation $g_{av} = 1/3 (g_{\parallel} + 2g_{\perp})$ and obtained values in the range 2.10 ± 0.05 . The $\langle g \rangle$ less than 2.3 indicating the covalent nature of the metal ligand bond in the complexes¹⁴ and suggesting a square planar geometry around copper(II).

FAB-mass spectral studies:

The FAB-mass spectrum^{19,20} of representative compound $[\text{Cu}(\text{sap})_2]$, showed an important peak at $m/z = 681, 458, 796$ which corresponds to the molecular weight of the compounds supported the composition of these complexes.

The FAB-mass fragmentation pattern of $[\text{Cu}(\text{sap})_2]$ as well as their spectrum have been given (Supplementary Scheme 1 and Fig. S3).

Experimental

Materials and methods:

All chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade quality. Anhydrous CuCl_2 (Sigma-Aldrich), $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2-aminopyridine, salicylaldehyde and naphthaldehyde (Merck), *o*-toluidine (BDH) were used without further purification. The solvents were dried before use according to prescribed procedure^{24,25}. The Schiff bases were prepared by reported methods²⁵⁻²⁷. The spectroscopic grade solvents were employed for recording the spectra. Chlorine content and copper was estimated by Volhard's method²⁸. IR spectra (4000–400) were recorded in Nujol; whereas 400–200 cm^{-1} spectrum was recorded in KBr solid, using Perkin-Elmer 1000 FTIR spectrometer. Electronic spectra of the compound were recorded in DMF and/or in $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6/\text{THF}$ on a Hitachi-

200 spectrophotometer. ESR spectrum was recorded on E-112 ESR spectrometer. TGA was recorded on Q-500 instrument. FAB mass spectrum was recorded on Jeol SX 102/AD-6000 mass spectrometer data system using argon/xenon (6 kv, 10 mA) the FAB-gas. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature (by Gouy's method).

Synthesis of complexes:

The complexes **1-5** of the type $[(\text{sb})_2\text{M} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ were synthesized by refluxing metal solution containing $\text{M}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with ethanolic solution of Schiff base in 1:2 molar ratio(s).

Synthesis of complexes $[(\text{sap})_2\text{Co} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (1):

An ethanolic solution of $\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.000 g, 4.01 mmol) mixed with ethanolic solution of salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (1.591 g, ~8.02 mmol). The reaction mixture was stirred and further refluxed on water bath for about 3 h. The complex thus isolated was collected on a sintered funnel washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. Green solid; yield: 68%, Found: C, 58.13; H, 4.82; N, 12.34. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{22}\text{CoN}_4\text{O}_4$: C, 58.66; H, 4.48; N, 11.81%; μ_{eff} , 4.91 B.M.

$[(\text{sap})_2\text{Cu} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (2): Brown solid; yield: 64%, Found: C, 58.24; H, 4.46; N, 11.21; Cu, 12.61. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{22}\text{CuN}_4\text{O}_4$: C, 58.35; H, 4.49; N, 11.34; Cu, 12.86%; μ_{eff} , 1.86 B.M.

$[(\text{nap})_2\text{Co} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (3): Brown solid; yield: 65%, Found: C, 65.10; H, 4.30; N, 9.23. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{26}\text{CoN}_4\text{O}_4$: C, 65.20; H, 4.45; N, 9.5%; μ_{eff} , 4.88 B.M.

$[(\text{nap})_2\text{Ni} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (4): Yellowish green; yield: 67%, Found: C, 65.36; H, 4.37; N, 9.43. Calcd. for

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$C_{32}H_{26}NiN_4O_4$: C, 65.62; H, 4.45; N, 9.51%; μ_{eff} , 3.02 B.M.

$[(nap)_2Cu.2H_2O]$ (5): Greenish brown; yield: 64%, Found: C, 64.43; H, 4.30; N, 9.41; Cu, 10.62. Calcd. for $C_{32}H_{26}CuN_4O_4$: C, 64.69; H, 4.41; N, 9.43; Cu, 10.70%; μ_{eff} , 1.91 B.M.

Copper complexes of the types $[(Cl)Cu(sb)]_2$ **6**, **8** and $[Cu(sb)_2]$ **7**, **9** were synthesized by using same procedure as follows:

Synthesis of $[(Cl)Cu(sap)]_2$ (6):

A freshly prepared sodium salt of salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (1.981 g, 9.996 mmol) was added to THF-benzene solution of anhydrous copper(II)chloride (1.344 g, 9.996 mmol) in 1:1 molar ratio with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to reflux for ~4 h. The precipitated NaCl was removed by filtration. The excess solvent was removed by distillation and remaining compound was dried under reduced pressure. Yield: 73%; Found: C, 47.82; H, 3.44; N, 9.77; Cl, 11.33; Cu, 20.99. Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{18}Cl_2Cu_2N_4O_2$: C, 48.72; H, 3.04; N, 9.47; Cl, 11.84; Cu, 21.49%.

$[Cu(sap)_2]$ (7): Green solid; yield, 68%; Found: C, 62.78; H, 3.82; N, 12.15; Cu, 13.72. Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{18}CuN_4O_2$: C, 62.94; H, 3.96; N, 12.23; Cu, 13.88%; μ_{eff} , 1.70 B.M.

$[(Cl)Cu(smab)]_2$ (8): Brown solid; yield, 63%; Found: C, 54.26; H, 3.87; N, 4.51; Cu, 20.49. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{24}Cl_2Cu_2N_2O_2$: C, 54.37; H, 3.91; N, 4.53; Cu, 20.55%; μ_{eff} , 1.60 B.M.

$[Cu(smab)_2]$ (9): Brown solid; yield, 70%; Found: C, 69.32; H, 4.89; N, 5.62; Cu, 13.00. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{24}CuN_2O_2$: C, 69.48; H, 5.00; N, 5.79; Cu, 13.13%; μ_{eff} , 1.72 B.M.

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